

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 61

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 61

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 61:0 For the choir director; on a stringed instrument. <i>A Psalm</i> of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 61:1 לְמִנְצֵחַ אֶל־נְגִינֹת לְדָוִד : 2 שְׁמְעָה אֱלֹהִים</p>
<p>Psa. 61:1 Hear my cry, O God; Give heed to my prayer.</p>	<p>רִנָּתִי הִקְשִׁיבָה תִּפְלְתִי : 3 מִקְצֵה הָאָרֶץ אֱלֹהֶיךָ אֶקְרָא</p>
<p>2 From the end of the earth I call to You when my heart is faint; Lead me to the rock that is higher than I.</p>	<p>בְּעֵטֶךָ לִבִּי בְּצוּר־יְרוּם מִמֶּנִּי תִנְחַנֵּי : 4 כִּי־הָיִיתָ</p>
<p>3 For You have been a refuge for me, A tower of strength against the enemy.</p>	<p>מִחֹסֶה לִּי מִגֹּדֶל־עֵז מִפְּנֵי אוֹיֵב : 5 אֲגוּרָה בְּאֶהְלֶךָ עוֹלָמִים אֲחֹסֶה בְּסֹתֶר</p>
<p>4 Let me dwell in Your tent forever; Let me take refuge in the shelter of Your wings. Selah.</p>	<p>כְּנֶפֶיךָ סֹלָה : 6 כִּי־אַתָּה אֱלֹהִים שָׁמַעְתָּ לְנַדְרֵי נַתַּף יְרֻשֶׁת יִרְאֵי שִׁמְךָ : 7 יָמִים</p>
<p>Psa. 61:5 For You have heard my vows, O God; You have given me the inheritance of those who fear Your name.</p>	<p>עַל־יָמֵי־מַלְךְ תּוֹסִיף שְׁנוֹתָיו כְּמוֹ־דָר וָדָר : 8 יֵשֶׁב עוֹלָם לִפְנֵי אֱלֹהִים תִּסְדַּר וְאַמֶּת מִן</p>
<p>6 You will prolong the king's life; His years will be as many generations.</p>	<p>יִנְצְרֶהוּ : 9 כִּן אֲזַמְרָה שִׁמְךָ לְעַד לְשִׁלְמֵי נַדְרֵי יוֹם </p>
<p>7 He will abide before God forever; Appoint lovingkindness and truth that they may preserve him.</p>	<p>יוֹם :</p>

<p>^s So I will ^asing praise to Your name forever, That I may ^bpay my vows day by day.</p>	
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References

Psalm 61:1

^aPs 64:1

^bPs 86:6

Psalm 61:2

^aPs 42:6

^bPs 77:3

^cPs 18:2; 94:22

Psalm 61:3

¹Lit *from*

^aPs 62:7

^bPs 59:9; Prov 18:10

Psalm 61:4

¹Or *sojourn*

²*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aPs 23:6; 27:4

^bPs 17:8; 91:4

Psalm 61:5

^aJob 22:27; Ps 56:12

^bDeut 28:58; Neh 1:11; Ps 86:11; 102:15; Is 59:19; Mal 2:5; 4:2

Psalm 61:6

¹Lit *add days to*

²Lit *days*

^aPs 21:4

Psalm 61:7

¹Or *sit enthroned*

^aPs 41:12

^bPs 40:11

Psalm 61:8

^aJudg 5:3; Ps 30:4; 33:2; 71:22

^bPs 65:1; Is 19:21

Targum

Psa. 61:1 For praise, with the psalms of David. ² Accept, O LORD, my petition, hear my prayer. ³ From the ends of the earth I will pray in your presence when my heart is weary; lead me to a strong fortress built on a rock that is higher than I. ⁴ For you have been security for me, in truth, a stronghold before the enemy. ⁵ I will dwell in your tent forever, I will be secure in the shade of your presence forever. ⁶ For you, O LORD, have heard my vows; you have given the inheritance to those who fear your name. ⁷ You will add days to the age to come, the days of the King Messiah; his years are like the generations of this age and the generations of the age to come. ⁸ He will dwell forever in the presence of the LORD; goodness and truth from the Lord of the World will guard him. ⁹ Therefore, will I praise your name forever, when I pay my vows in the day of the redemption of Israel, and in the day the King Messiah is anointed to be king.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

This Psalm demonstrates that no distance or danger could diminish David's fervent love for the LORD.

Verse one

נְגִינָה (n'geenat) – means “instruments.” In the context of this verse, this word denotes tones of a song inspired by and suited for all the various situations of physical and spiritual life.

David is speaking of the impact of his musical gifts, which exceeded his accomplishments as a warrior.

To the Sefirah Netzach who offers victory, upon the tones of song, a Psalm of David.

Verse two

Hear, O God, the outpouring of my spirit; attend to my prayer.

Verse three

The mind controls the body, which is visible to the outside world. If the spirit is weak, it will withdraw and hide behind the physical body. Therefore, a person needs a strong body and spirit.

**If I call upon You from the end of the land when my heart shrouds itself,
You will lead me to a rock that would be too high for me to ascend alone.**

Verses four and five

In moments of anguish and weakness, it is good to know that one can rely on the LORD to be there.

**For You have become a refuge for me, a tower of fortitude in the face of
the enemy.**

**So I shall endeavor to dwell in Your tent forever, even when I shall rest
hidden beneath the shade of your wings, as I trustingly hope to do.
Meditate on this verse.**

Verse six

David believed that his spiritual activities were his life's pledge and that the LORD accepted it with favor.

**For you, O God, have heard my vows: You have granted them the
heritage of those that fear Your Name.**

Verse seven

David believed that the LORD gave him a longer life because of his spiritual activities. There is a midrash that says that Adam was shown David's rule and Adam decided to give David 25 years of his life.

You will add to my days as king; You will let his years be as the succession of generations.

Verse eight

David calls for the love and truth of the Sefirah Chesed for the time that he is on the throne of Israel.

But if he is to dwell before God forever, have the Sefirah Chesed place mercy and truth upon me.

Verse nine

Thus I will sing praises unto Your Name throughout all time, in order to perform my vows day by day.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach who offers victory, upon the tones of song, a Psalm of David.
Hear, O God, the outpouring of my spirit; attend to my prayer.

If I call upon You from the end of the land when my heart shrouds itself, You will lead me to a rock that would be too high for me to ascend alone.

For You have become a refuge for me, a tower of fortitude in the face of the enemy.

So I shall endeavor to dwell in Your tent forever, even when I shall rest hidden beneath the shade of your wings, as I trustingly hope to do. Meditate on this verse.

For you, O God, have heard my vows: You have granted them the heritage of those that fear Your Name.

You will add to my days as king; You will let his years be as the succession of generations.

But if he is to dwell before God forever, have the Sefirah Chesed place mercy and truth upon me.

Thus I will sing praises unto Your Name throughout all time, in order to perform my vows day by day.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

